

Climate Risk Information for Supporting ADaptation Planning and operation – Phase II

CIMATE SERVICES DESCRIPTION

1. Product and services

1.1. The product

The main [CRISI-ADAPT-II](#) product is a holistic-based decision-support tool that is offered as a specialised climate service to validate adaptation planning and operations. This tool consists of two modules, the Climate Risk Information Tool (CRIT) and the Monitoring Extreme Events Tool (MEET).

These modules enable end-users to improve their decisions to face climate-related impacts with adaptation planning or to identify new opportunities for improving efficiency in their operations.

1.2. The values

1.2.1. Included services

The values provided on the CRISI-ADAPT II project can be summarized on the CRIT&MEET platform, which are based on its derivate products and services. The platform aims to support decision making to reduce climate-related impacts and increase resource efficiency. The main functionalities are:

- 1) Monitoring climate-related hazards across all the timescales (from weather to climate)
- 2) Management of vulnerable elements and their climate sensitivity (resilience).
- 3) Possibility* of risk assessment according to the points 1 and 2.
- 4) Possibility** of Cost-Benefit-Analysis of adaptation measures based on the point 3.
- 5) Validation of adaptation measures thanks to the Early Warning System of point 1.

* Some natural hazards, such as flooding and reservoir water scarcity, could require specific hydrological modelling that is offered as an additional service. Other climate hazards like meteorological drought, heat waves, extreme winds and fogs are included by default.

** The platform is prepared to integrate the Cost-Benefit-Analysis according to the points 1-3, but specific information and adjustments could be required in an additional service.

The current state of the platform covers four sectors: a) water management for supply, agriculture and environment, b) flooding and emergency response, c) energy planning, d) port infrastructures and operations. In addition, the platform presents GIS-based features with very flexible functionalities:

- The platform stands out for its constant updating capacity, which translates into improving the quality and reliability of information on vulnerability and risk in the territory.
- The system offers the possibility of providing information from web services (WMS-OGC) in accordance with the European INSPIRE directive.
- The platform has a data model fully adaptable to the needs of each administration, with possibility of managing large volumes of information with a variety of topics: infrastructure, heritage, natural elements, etc.
- Allows the management of information with different profiles (view, edit, validate). Special attention has been paid to the quality of the data, introducing a validation phase to ensure it.
- The system converts the data into dynamic maps and, through highly optimized automation, immediate recalculation of the derived risk indices is performed.
- The platform presents a simple interface adapted to all users. It allows a comfortable handling of the layers, with filtering and searches, consultations and editing on the screen. The selection of symbology has been careful to be clear and useful.

1.2.2. Additional services

Additional climate services are those ones that are not included in the Essential Climate Services directly provided by the CRIT&MEET functionalities. Their specific definition and scope is provided by the head of each service:

- **Statistical downscaling of climate projections (FIC):** Climate scenarios downscaled at a local scale are directly offered by the [CRIT&MEET platform](#), according to a standard bias correction (empirical quantile-quantile mapping) between CMIP6 Earth System Models and the ERA5-Land reanalysis. For some regions and for local risk assessment, however, this approach presents important limitations (e.g. local precipitation regimes with foehn effect); and therefore it is advisable to apply a more sophisticated approach such as the FICLIMA method, based on a two-step analogue/regression method with parametric correction (Ribalaygua *et al.* 2013, Monjo *et al.* 2014, 2016).
- **Urban flood modelling (Aquatec):** The CRIT&MEET tool will be able to provide rainfall information considering space variability for short, midterm and long-time horizons. In order to provide specific information about the potential magnitude of floods in flood prone areas and the related socio-economic impacts, this complementary service proposes the development and calibration of hydrodynamic and urban drainage models (including 2D overland flow models and/or 1D drainage model) and the performance of a comprehensive flood risk assessment (including socio-economic impacts).
- **Hydrological drought modelling (Meteogrid):** Meteorological drought is a climate-related hazard included in the CRIT&MEET platform, according to the Standard Precipitation (and Evapotranspiration) Index (SPI/SPEI) (Vicente *et al.*, 2010). However, for some risk analysis it is required to analyse water balance in river flows or water quality in reservoirs. For this

reason, an additional service is defined to provide simulations on hydrological drought. For this purpose, the monthly flow of the rivers of the studied basins can be modeled through the hydrological model GR available in the library *r* called AirGR (Coron *et al.*, 2017).

- **Cost-benefit Analysis (CBA) (NE):** This complementary service helps to evaluate adaptation options of cases in their related sectors. It is a widely spread assessment method that allows the possibility to translate social and environmental impacts into monetary values. For the cost benefit analysis decisions are made based on the optimal ratio of the costs of the investment (i.e. measures) to benefits (reduction in damage potential). Here, all costs are expressed in monetary terms, and are adjusted for the time value of money. The ratio obtained in a CBA is based on pure monetary benefit and investments.
- **Mitigation and adaptation plan (CEA):** This complementary service makes use of the outcomes of the CRIT&MEET platform and the risk assessment and offers customised mitigation and adaptation measures for each stakeholder/location. If this service is requested by a Local Authority, the mitigation and adaptation actions can be formulated in a plan following the guidelines of the Covenant of Mayors (CoM) so that it can be submitted as a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) to the CoM's platform.

1.3. End users

1.3.1. Identification of needs, co-design and co-creation

The CRISI-ADAPT II participation process with challenge owners has an important role on the project development, consequently, an exhaustive interaction process has been designed to identify their needs through the co-design and co-creation procedures.

The project outputs are destined to both regional/local authorities and the private sector. These two categories have different needs and abilities for using our services. Additionally, the final product can be offered to an extensive number of sectors, concretely to all those who are perceived as vulnerable to recent and future changes resulting from climate change or consumption trends or resource availability: This includes public services or infrastructures (ports, roads, etc.), the water sector (treatment, supply and sanitation), energy (generation and supply) and basic value chains (production and commercialization), among others. For example, in the area of water availability (agriculture, drinking water), CRISI-ADAPT II will propose an improvement of the user's resilience based on several axes, such as prevention against climate trends or the optimization of the network and distribution, thus improving the user's personal and economic prevention and contributing to enhancing environmental sustainability. Climate change issues are expected to remain or even increase, and innovative and adaptive solutions around this question could be an important way to save goods and even lives.

During the early stages of CRISI-ADAPT (2018 and 2019), the project aimed to pre-identify needs and actors to learn about their perceptions on climate-related challenges. Throughout the duration of the project, they are actively collaborating with the tool developers' team in obtaining the best scalable solution for their problems.

1.3.2. Channels and communications

In order to increase the outreach of the project results, the agreement will distinguish between free accessible results and payment services. The first ones will serve to raise awareness among citizens against climate change impacts, but also as a claim to know the existence of the project results, including the climate services. CRISI-ADAPT II will provide a democratisation of climate-related risk information required by each end-user. That is, the benefits of the project outputs will be expanded and transparently used to support the adaptation and risk reduction activities planned by city governments, modellers, investors and traders related to all sectors potentially affected by climatic impacts (challenge owners).

Most of the free accessible data will correspond to the public versions of the project deliverables, as well as basic climate data (little post-processed from the Copernicus platform, for instance), available in: <https://www.ficlima.org/intercambio/indexed/crisiadapt/data/>

The payment services are properly the Climate Services developed during the project, especially the functionalities of the CRIT and MEET modules and all the information used as an input and obtained as an output of the simulations of climate-related impacts, cost-benefit analysis, adaptation planning, etc.

The communication channels to provide all the results will be mainly (1) social media for the freely accessible online data and (2) direct demonstrations of the tool functionalities for payment services. The last channel will correspond especially to online and face-to-face workshops but other can be considered.

1.3.3. Price of the services

Each new customer can acquire the CRIT module during the first year of service. This is required to develop a possible MEET service. In this case, the MEET module can be acquired during the following years. However, all CRISI-ADAPTII challenge owners can directly acquire the annual MEET service from the first year, because **CRIT service is included in the project**.

The price of the CRIT module is about 15-50k€ (depending on the area extension to be applied), paid only once, while the MEET service is also 15-50k€ but per year (Table 1). The exact formula is:

$$Price = \begin{cases} 15,000€ & \text{if Surface} \leq 1,000km^2 \\ 1666.67€ * \left[\log_{10} \left(\frac{Surface}{km^2} \right) \right]^2 & \text{if Surface} > 1,000km^2 \end{cases}$$

Table 1. Prices of Essential Climate Services of CRIT & MEET in Europe (taxes are not included, because they depend on each country).

Market launch for Site cases	CRIT	CRIT+MEET
	Once-time price (first year)	Price per year (from second year)
Local case ($\leq 1,000 km^2$)	15,000*	15,000* €/year
Medium case (7,500 km ²)	25,027*	25,027* €/year
Large case (80,000 km ²)	40,068*	40,068* €/year

*A discount between 10% and 30% may be applied from the second Site hired by the same client.

Additional climate services are defined by the consortium (or part of this) to customise extra products (e.g. local climate scenarios, specific hydrological modelling, detailed cost-benefit analysis, adaptation plan, etc.), but is not included in the **general price**. Find the specific extra services in Table 2.

Table 2. Additional climate services, complementary to CRIT&MEET. They can be contracted separately each one, but after contracting CRIT or MEET. Revenues will be directly received by each provider.

Name of the service	Provider	Description	Price
Statistical downscaling of climate projections	FIC	Application of the FICLIMA statistical downscaling method to CMIP6 climate projections at a local scale for one observed time-series with at least 5-year length.	7,000€
Urban flood modelling	Aquatec	Based on previous existing hydrodynamic and urban drainage models, development and calibration of 2D flooding surface models and perform of flood risk assessment including socio-economic impacts.	25,000€
Hydrological drought modelling	Meteogrid	Application of hydrological modelling to simulate water balance in a river flow or water quality in a reservoir.	12,000€
Cost-benefit analysis	Nomisma energia	Provision of a cost benefit analysis. This service is offered to support decisions based on the optimal ratio of the costs of the investment (i.e. measures) to benefits (reduction in damage potential). Here, all costs are expressed in monetary terms, and are adjusted for the time value of money	8,000€
Mitigation and adaptation plan	CEA	Development of mitigation and adaptation plan at a local scale (small municipality)	5,000 €

2. References

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